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The Practice of Closed-loop Economics and Paradoxes of Value Creation on Used Platforms: Using the Example of Vinted

KEYWORDS

circular economy,
second-hand platforms,
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value creation,
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population and control ecology,
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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The growth of the second-hand goods market and the development of electronic platforms contribute to convenience, environmental sustainability, and economic development. Researching these platforms is important for understanding their mechanisms, improving efficiency, and protecting consumers.

Research aim: to examine the practices and strategies of second-hand goods platforms that contribute to the development of a circular economy.

Materials and Methods. The study used research articles from international peer-reviewed journals covering topics in the textile industry, business and consumer behavior, sustainability, waste management, e-commerce, fashion marketing, platform models, and environmental economics. The study also used conference proceedings, including the collections "Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering" and "Lecture Notes in Computer Science" (Springer), among others.

Results. Over the past 10 years, secondhand digital platforms such as Vinted have successfully developed new approaches to circularity along the "Earn money and save the planet by selling what you don't wear" argument. This article examines how circularity (and economic benefits are) is integrated into company's business model. Specifically, it discusses the paradoxes inherent to the value creation and value capture-extraction mechanisms. Likewise, through a critical analysis of the constituents of its business model, particularly company's vision and what we considered to be an implicit predatory pricing strategy, this article outlined a possible scenario for the equilibrium of the whole ecosystem along its interactions with clothing companies.

Conclusion. The e-retail platform Vinted has built an economic model that promotes and facilitates the rationalization of resources for their most productive (recycled) use, while simultaneously (ostensibly) expanding their social productivity. It is not an industrial system that is intentionally regenerative, but a platform that replaces the concept of "end-of-life" with reuse.

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INTRODUCTION

Interest in used goods markets is currently growing significantly, driven by socioeconomic and environmental factors. Electronic platforms that provide an interface for selling and buying such goods are gaining popularity because of their convenience, speed, and accessibility. Their development is expanding opportunities for market participants, enabling them to find and sell goods quickly, and it is stimulating the creation of new economic models. The environmental aspect is important: reselling used items promotes the rational use of resources and reduces waste, which meets modern sustainability challenges. The development of these platforms facilitates the creation of new jobs and business initiatives, which positively affects economic stability. Studying the functioning of such platforms allows us to identify key mechanisms of their operation, determine the impact of technologies on market conditions, and develop strategies for improving efficiency and protecting consumer rights. Therefore, research into electronic platforms for the sale of used goods is a pressing issue, essential for both the theoretical analysis of the e-commerce market and the practical development of innovative solutions. P. D. Sumo et al. write that the used clothing trade is an important supply chain linking developed and developing countries and a valuable alternative to clothing consumption for people experiencing economic decline, poverty, and low purchasing power. The authors believe that used clothing plays a crucial role in delivering fashionable products to customers in underdeveloped African countries. It also creates jobs for hundreds of thousands of people in retail, distribution, repair, laundry, and recycling [1]. There are a significant number of factors influencing the purchase of used clothing, both online and offline: low price, defects, brand, uniqueness, a desire to be more environmentally friendly, etc.

N. A. Mobarak et al. examine how consumers' perceptions of used clothing influence their decision to switch from new to used clothing, integrating theories of perceived risk and consumer behavior when switching from new to used clothing [2]. L. B. Frahm et al. summarize the literature on barriers to and motivations for second-hand consumption. According to the authors, the dynamics of second-hand consumption depend on the context, shopping experience, and type of product, rather than their category [3]. X. Chen & T. Tabata found that the main motives for purchasing second-hand clothing are financial benefits and the desire to follow fashion trends [4]. A. Toftegaard & N. Søgaaard demonstrate that the

level of monetary benefit (high or low) from purchasing second-hand clothing significantly influences consumers' unconsciousness in decision making and their tendency to over-consume. The researchers suggest these findings challenge the assumed sustainability of used clothing markets. They reveal that imperfect substitution occurs when consumers buy used clothing alongside new clothing instead of replacing new items. T. A. Dar and T. A. Wani found that religiosity predicts expected guilt, thriftiness, and environmental awareness, which shape attitudes toward used clothing. These factors mediate the relationship between religiosity and purchase intention [6]. I. Dimassi & F. Smaoui note a renewed interest in luxury consumption, particularly with the increase in luxury sales in alternative second-hand markets [7]. K. A. Schuck et al. examine various aspects of consumer perceptions of used luxury goods. The researchers discuss how luxury brands should respond to the growing importance of the second-hand market and the growing demand for more sustainable product options [8].

Factors influencing online purchases of used clothing also include seller reputation, reviews, return policies, ease of search, etc. H. Ijuin & A. Ishigaki believe that the expansion of the used goods market on e-commerce platforms helps reduce product waste [9]. According to A. Ilmalhaq et al., conscious consumer behavior includes purchasing used clothing. The authors point to a significant positive direct impact of online recommendations on environmental attitudes, consumer engagement, and conscious consumer behavior [10]. L. Monteiro et al. emphasize the influence of social media engagement, influenced endorsement, transparent sustainability communication, and circular business models on the behavior of used goods buyers [11]. J. Park et al. study the factors determining transaction satisfaction and intention to use local platforms for selling used goods. Scholars emphasize the importance of social factors in shaping transaction satisfaction and intention to use the platform [12]. N. Luo et al. provide a useful finding for e-commerce platforms, suggesting that sellers of used goods can employ dual strategies—either using trust signals (reputation and comments) or value signals (brand-price tradeoffs) [13]. N. das Virgens et al. examine the contribution of used clothing sales to reducing negative environmental effects in a circular economy [14]. C. Calvo-Porrá et al. study the factors that determine consumer behavior when purchasing used goods online. According to the researchers, when purchasing used goods online, consumers are driven by environmental motives, followed by trust in the online store and economic factors

[15]. T. Xu et al. conclude that emotional rather than social presence contributes to online second-hand purchase behavior by increasing trust in the platform and the seller [16]. L. J. Thomas et al. also emphasize prizing affective and emotional aspects in sustainable consumption [17].

Among the disadvantages of buying used clothing online are the lack of opportunity to try on the items, the risk of receiving defective items, difficulties with returns, etc. B. Parker and R. Weber question the ability of online retailers to replace used clothing stores, which have traditionally relied on a loyal local customer base and a personalized shopping experience [18].

Thus, research shows that perceptions of risk, motivations (financial benefit, fashion), and the level of economic benefit significantly influence consumer decisions when choosing used clothing. These factors influence both the motivation to purchase and attitudes toward the used clothing market, highlighting the complexity and diversity of motives and barriers in this segment. Research also shows that the used clothing market, particularly through online platforms, contributes to reducing waste and increasing consumer environmental awareness. Social factors, trust and effective communication, as well as seller strategies based on reputation and value for money, play an important role.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was based on research articles from peer-reviewed international journals: *Textile Research Journal*; *Future Business Journal* (business research, including consumer behavior); *Circular Economy and Sustainability* (sustainable development and circular economy); *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management* (material and waste recycling); *Discover Sustainability* (sustainable development research and practices); *Electronic Commerce Research* (e-commerce research); *Journal of Global Fashion Marketing* (marketing in the global fashion industry); *Proper* (a scientific publication focused on platform models and innovation); *Nature* (a journal covering environmental and economic issues), and many others.

The study also used materials from international conferences: *Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering* (Springer); and *Lecture Notes in Computer Science* (Springer) in computer science. Publications on platform models—“International Conference on Enterprise Design, Operations, and Computing”, etc.

RESULTS

Outdoor clothing, home retailing, consumer goods, fashion, flooring, personal computer manufacturing, and a growing number of industries have been infused by circular economy practices. Besides dowagers such as Patagonia, Ikea, Unilever, Accenture, H&M, and Adidas, over the past 10 years, new companies and competitors have entered the ecosystem with business models based on a balance between sustainability and economic benefits that materialized in value propositions that aim to lower the effect of human activity on the environment.

Furthermore, promoting and advocating for companies to embrace a circular economy and customers to engage in more ecological consumption has recently overlapped with changes in the socio-economic context. First, due to the economic crisis, consumption patterns have evolved towards discovering alternative channels, reassessing buying, and counting on discounts [19]. Second, as highlighted by L'Observatoire Cetelem (2023/2024) [20], the sentiment that purchasing power has significantly deteriorated has increased similarly to the rise in inflation rates in most European countries.

These parallel trend curves have created a context conducive to the growth of secondhand platforms such as Vinted driven by the argument that is to “have fun by saving money and doing something for the planet” (Picture 1). If it aims to reflect a balance of economic, environmental, and social needs, the underlying business model challenges the normative principles of value creation and idealized views of meeting sustainability expectations, as its core activity is limited to reuse.

Terminé !

Merci de ton achat sur Vinted ! En optant pour de la seconde main, tu te fais plaisir et tu fais un geste pour la planète.

[Publier un article](#)

Picture 1 Message appears on a buyer's page once a transaction is definitively validated

Secondhand platform's approach to circularity, through a unique dimension that is reuse, and value-generating processes, is an under-researched study domain. Consequently, this calls for an in-depth exploratory methodology of a single case that is Vinted. The qualitative research process implemented here is grounded on a lived-in experience: through an immersion in the buying/selling routines of platform users and buyer/seller-machine interactions (that is to say an extensive usage of the Vinted app), it aims to facilitate a more efficient identification and understanding of platform's value creation/capture/extraction mechanisms. The analysis is backed by existing scholarly studies on circularity and business models, value creation/capture/extraction, and population and control ecology. More fundamentally, the dialectic echoes the recommendations of Siggelkow [21] for whom a (single) case-study research design "derives its excitement and justification through little more than the description of a particular phenomenon" (p. 20).

Accordingly, this paper engages in a critical appraisal of how secondhand platforms such as Vinted embed circularity into their business model. The latter concept serves as support for discussing by what means a company generates economic value in a particular business by articulating the value proposition definition, value creation, and delivery mechanisms, coupled with modes of capturing value [22]. The analysis proceeds from the premise that a firm's business model echoes a constructivist posture, meaning that the company, aware of its strengths and weaknesses, seeks to develop the most effective strategies [in particular by exploiting others' assets] so as to obtain, with a minimum investment, the maximum effect, namely an increasing volume of users [sensitive to both price and more sustainable consumption behaviors] and transactions.

Finally, by referring to population ecology principles, we envision possible alterations that may be induced in the business ecosystem of the clothing industry [23]. It is probably in the latter business domain that the impact of second-hand platforms is most marked because it is the result of complex interactions that underlie the purchase of second-hand clothing, the paradoxes emanating from communication of the platform, and the strategies implemented to appropriate the benefits resulting from circularity but also their potential consequences on the ecosystem, which leads to nuance of the benefits of the circular economy. The perimeter of the analysis is limited to France, which is Vinted's primary market.

The business model of Vinted

Antiquity, secondhand or thrift shopping allowed people to afford items otherwise inaccessible. In the Middle Ages, this form of commerce was structured by the creation of real marketplaces, 'flea markets', which were places of exchange where individuals could sell, buy, and barter used goods. The underlying reasoning is a form of democratization because at that time, only wealthy people (belonging to nobility or the rich bourgeoisie) had the financial means to pay for new clothes fairly regularly.

For a little over a decade, the second-hand industry has entered the Modern Age, one in which the increasing breadth and depth of the offer meets interest for a sustainable fashion consumption and the circular economy. The underlying principle is that clothes can be (almost) endlessly re-used "without harm or waste".

Created in 2008 in Lithuania, the digital platform Vinted is currently the leading peer-to-peer second-hand marketplace in Europe, based on a community of 105 million [24] buyers/sellers of second-hand items (new items are also on sale). It has been established in 15 countries, and France is its main market in terms of the number of customers (16 million [25]). In 2023, Vinted recorded a 61% increase in revenue compared to 2022 (€596.3 million vs. €370.2 million [26]) and reached profitability for the first time since the company was created (net profit in 2023 was €17.8 million vs. a net loss in 2022 of €20.4 million [27]).

It is well accepted that the first digitalization wave that occurred in the mid-90s with companies such as Amazon (e-retailing) and eBay (peer-to-peer economics) has already set business model innovation standards. As part of the turn to an information economy, the focus was put on demand [28]. On the other hand, embracing circularity has led companies to develop new business models. Scholarly literature has agreed that a circular business model is "a business model in which the conceptual logic for value creation is based on utilizing the economic value retained in products after use in the production of new offerings" [29, p. 2]. Vinted's business model does not adhere to this definition, and it has re-shifted the marketplace dynamics with an emphasis on supply. The canvas we use here to explore the relevant dimensions related to Vinted is derived from the taxonomies proposed by Bartels et al. [30] and Mentink [31] and adapted to the object under study (Table 1).

Table 1

Vinted business model constituents

	Vinted
What vision?	Vinted, like Decathlon in the distribution of sporting goods) and eBay in the auction market, has "democratized" access to the second-hand market. By adding a circular dimension, the platform constitutes the matrix of an alternative vision of the circular economy based on an old/new transaction system that turns goods at the end of their service life into resources for others, thus closing loops in industrial processes. Ownership is here a transitional concept and, as such, it has changed the economic logic that has dominated the business world by substituting production for sufficiency (limited to reuse) [32].
Value proposition	It is expressed in company's corporate communications: "Together, we're making the change to second-hand. Second-hand is better than new for the climate, for your wardrobe, and for your wallet. That's why we want to make it first choice for everyone [33]." It is based on an unusual association between economics-oriented and sustainability goals, and the underlying rationale is to push individuals to build a new relationship with goods through temporary ownership that ultimately intends to save energy [34].
Price	First, pricing is built on the principle that it should not constitute a barrier to membership in the community, so there are neither platform membership fees nor direct commissions on transactions. Second, different incentive mechanisms promote the downward adjustment of prices in relation to demand . This aggressive pricing strategy combined with the opportunistic use of imperfect information about product quality illustrates a form of rational predation that aims to increase the users' base through a sale/gain prospect while inhibiting existing members from leaving the community because it might mean accepting losses.
Revenue model	The platform acts as a mediator between users through a pure sales and value capture/extraction model: reselling increasing volumes of products (i.e., not retrieving products after first life from the market) and generating revenues from mandatory services associated with each sale. It also derives revenue from the third parties to whom it sells the advertising space.
A closed value system that relies on others' resources	According to the resource-based view of the firm, secondhand platforms are considered as a subsystem of various ecosystems or industries that provide it two types of assets they need to survive: branded products and buyers/sellers (users).
Customer's role	It is not customer-centric but supply side-oriented. Through a temporary ownership model, Vinted ultimately replaced the concept of the consumer with that of the user.
Goods on sale and associated services	Vinted has partly taken over and extended the eBay model: hosting of personal pages to present one's objects to be sold, within-platform search capabilities, speed of processing, and posting of sales announcements. Unlike eBay, Vinted does not continuously enrich its platform by creating new categories of items for sale. Newly created services are immediately monetized (luxury item verification service, buyer insurance, basic retail push practices, such as top of the list/shelves optional fees, etc.).
Cost management and investments	Search for economies of scale and scope: cost reduction has recently materialized through automatization and maximization of (market share) community size. For the moment, besides the acquisition of several competitors, financial surpluses are largely reinvested in existing assets rather than creating new ones.

<p>Litigation and complaint handling</p>	<p>The platform primarily uses automatic detection algorithms and whistleblowing to identify, in particular, the presence of counterfeits and double accounts. Initially, disputes between users are managed by the users themselves. Second, a dedicated service intervenes according to a set of rules that are often difficult to read, and whose interpretation can give rise to unsatisfactory decisions for one of the parties involved in the transaction. These processes prove to be inefficient and slow, and lead to unjustified decisions that largely explain the negative ratings given to the platform by users on the Trustpilot site [35].</p>
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Ingrained in its business model is a worldview that “Second-hand is the future.” Implicitly, it is difficult to see in Vinted's vision of the future of the second-hand marketplace any commitment to a business philosophy that considers the economy as an interlocking living system. By uniquely focusing on a buy-and-(re)sell approach, such business model uses transaction-based streams not to generate a revitalized productive economy but to maintain “an expanded extractive or ‘rentier’ economy which is parasitical” [36, p. 115].

The paradoxical approach to value creation of Vinted

How circular economy initiatives can generate economic value for a company, principally through recycling, is well documented in the existing literature (e.g., Ranta, Aarikka-Stenroos and Mäkinen [37]). Secondhand digital platforms such as Vinted, which have inserted circularity into their business models through reuse, have received less attention and consequently deserve further scrutiny. In this regard, the seminal quote from Brandenburger and Nalebuff [38] that “whereas creating value is an inherently cooperative process, capturing value is inherently competitive” plainly summarizes Vinted's approach to value creation: it is competitive by essence. The aim is twofold: it is economics-oriented [preserving market power over competition to indirectly increase profitability] and volume-related [multiplying transactions] (Guiltinan and Gundlach [39]).

Capturing value from reputational capital and extracting value from users

In the ecosystem to which Vinted belongs, the mechanism for capturing value is basically based on exploiting the reputational capital of the owner companies of the products on sale on the platform. In a setting based on second-party assets (branded products), reputational capital aims to facilitate survival in ways that keep up over time [40]. In the absence of their own resources, enhancing transactional trust

in such assets is essential to enable operations within the platform as they 'radiate' the minds of reciprocally influencing consumers/users [41]. The status and perceived quality of reputable companies such as, for instance, Ralph Lauren, Nike, Tommy Hilfiger, and The North Face theoretically drive repeated transactions. Thus, Vinted effectively captures a portion of the value collectively created by these companies during their historical course, but also captures value through users' reuse/resell actions as extra stages of the value-creation process along the extended lifetime value cycle of products within the platform.

The platform extracts value along the buy-(re)use-sell cycle, as every purchase/sale is associated with mandatory (shipping costs, buyer protection fees) and optional (products highlighted in digital shelves, etc.) services. First, it is supported by a product-oriented strategy, whose endeavor is to grow the flow of goods on sale on the platform, with the fundamental difference that sourcing is carried out by the users, which allows cost savings for the company. Second, sales-based repeated transactions are encouraged by a push-marketing approach that predominantly relies on a company's incentive messages (Picture 2). Combined with an aggressive price strategy, the buy-and-resell cycle gives the misleading impression that the products on sale are 'possibly constantly' on promotion which is likely to attract more and more users hoping to 'get a good deal.'

Picture 2 "Item on sale - Do you know that you sell faster when you have more items in your closet? - Add another article/Later"

This whole process could be characterized by literally 'siphoning' value off from other stakeholders both outside and inside the company [42] by dint of the

reputational capital of items on sale and from each transaction operated by users. The outcome of this approach to economic value generation is a manipulation of the competitive market processes to the firm's benefit through a price strategy that may be considered predatory, as it aims to create a dominant position built on an ever-increasing volume of users and products on sale.

A paradoxical situation

Such a volume strategy and its corollary, which is a race for gigantism, aim to achieve a quasi-monopolistic situation within the ecosystem. Nonetheless, its value capture/extraction mechanisms contain several paradoxical aspects.

While buyers have virtually access to more affordable products, advocating the development of sustainable behavior somewhat collides with the consumption habits (developed on and stimulated by the platform) that support an untenable "take, make, dispose" clothing cycle [43] because the company actually gets no benefit from closing the material loop. Indeed, extracting value from each transaction is based on the active participation of users, as they are interested in obtaining (even) a (minimal) pecuniary gain from the good bought or not on the platform before it reaches its end of life. Thus, sales are encouraged on the platform through communication based on financial incentives (Picture 3). As prices go along a downward spiral, Vinted pushes its users to sell more products, as revenue streams come from shipping costs and "buyer protection" fees.

Envie de gagner plus d'argent ?

Plus tu publies d'articles, plus les acheteurs te trouveront facilement.

[Publier un article >](#)

Picture 3 "Want to earn more money? - The more items you publish, the easier buyers will find you. - Publish an article >"

Unexpectedly, the combined effect of pricing strategy and uncertainty about product quality features inherent to digital secondhand marketplaces are the main characteristics that hinder 'welfare-enhancing transactions' between users. On the

one hand, operating a predatory pricing strategy creates a crescent imbalance between value creation and value extraction [44], as it engenders exchange inequity between users. On the other hand, although the platform provides a self-quality assessment grid that acts both as an incentive and as a means to limit distrust, knowledge about the 'quality' of goods remains asymmetrically distributed with some agents being naturally and transiently better informed than others [45]. Vinted proposes some sort of ex-post remediation if the buyer is not satisfied with the purchase; however, this compensating mechanism is rarely used and mainly materializes in downgrading the final evaluation. Indirectly, a user's score (on a 1 to 5 scale) moderates transactional uncertainty.

This situation leads to the known phenomenon of anti-selection or adverse selection described by Akerlof in its canonical book *The Market for Lemons* [46]. Applied to a secondhand digital marketplace, it will in all likelihood lead users, faced with the difficulty of understanding the content and actual quality of the products put on sale, to lower prices as much as possible until they reach an 'average price' resulting from the average of the prices of good and bad purchase options.

Somewhat ironically, (downward) price fluctuations are not supported by the company in the sense that they do not harm the company's profitability but are handled by community members, Vinted simply encouraging the phenomenon by allowing reduction proposals of up to 40%. Recently, the platform has introduced a more moderated approach by directly displaying discounts of 10%, 20% or 'at your choice.' Thus, by decoupling platform revenues from prices, Vinted does not renounce short-term benefits in favor of long-term profits.

The consequences, not necessarily desired, may be twofold: a marketplace (and more generally the entire ecosystem) in which the products at the lowest price (and therefore, probably, the worst) 'eliminate' all others, and users become less and less quality sensitive or willing to pay a "fair price," perceived quality being progressively excluded from the value creation equation. Thus, under such conditions, if the aggressive pricing policy stimulated by the company initially offers lower prices to users, this behavior may, in the long term, resemble predation and ultimately have undesirable consequences for the well-being of users (see Guiltinan and Gundlach, 1996).

Transactional vs. relational approach to value creation

As the linear economy emerged, value creation for customer basics has been progressively codified and set as a fundamental principle driving any business activity. There is no reason to believe that the circular economy has made them irrelevant.

The name of the brands, price, and retailer reputation have long been considered as 'marketing universals' that signal the quality of a product [47]. On the one hand, one may agree that they serve as universally shared features that facilitate Vinted penetration in target countries and thus contribute to the corporate objectives of growing internationally. On the other hand, most are not operative signs in its case because there are no own corporate credibility enhancers that will reduce uncertainty and protect users against transactional risks by guaranteeing a form of 'a priori quality.' This is likely due to the fact that Vinted targets everyone and it is profit-oriented meaning that the platform consistently spends less on crafting an upper-level corporate brand.

In other words, to overcome the subjectivity of quality cues, status sensitivity, and value consciousness, which may vary across countries, Vinted has 'globally' standardized its approach to European markets by deliberately and opportunistically choosing to focus on price as a universal cultural bond. De facto, the company has adopted a supply side stance instead of a customer-centric perspective on secondhand digital selling. In this view, exchange may become ever less socially justified because not both parties involved will be in a better position after the transaction is enacted. This condition is the prerogative of monopolistic situations, dominated by discrepancies. Consequently, exchange takes on the role of the transfer of values to the detriment of creative function.

Moreover, the intrinsic logic of such a model is dominated by instrumental value and one of its primary facets that is temporary ownership. Although circular products were supposed to be ownership-based [48], transactions on the platform require users to give up the condition of ownership and newness, and to engage in behaviors such as restoring and sending back goods [49].

Further arguments are provided in the literature on consumer engagement in online environments. In reality, it is more accurate to speak here of involvement, as there is little if no "cognitive and affective commitment to an active relationship with the brand as personified by the website" [50, p. 5], which characterizes engagement. One of the consequences of the very nature of the platform's activity is that interactive relationships are developed within users which precludes the emergence of an individual's perceived experiential value mirroring "the benefits derived from perceptions of playfulness, aesthetics, customer "return on investment" and service excellence" [51, p. 39]. This phenomenon is accentuated by the price strategy and narrative scheme implemented by the company that is not designed to communicate any brand value. On the contrary, it sustains a

cognitive process at the end of which the user's level of perceived “instrumental value” (i.e., utility and relevance) of an exchange supplants that of “experiential value” (i.e., emotional congruence) [52].

While the creation of value for the customer had always been associated with collaboration and mutual benefits, secondhand platforms business models, opportunistically using non-price benefits such as waste reduction to engage users into sustainable consumption behaviors, have finally opposed the rationality of decision making, that is to say making the best possible decision under incomplete information about product quality circumstances, to the anthropology of emotions, understood here as (the absence of) a reflection on and a consideration of the ritual dimension of emotions and its communicative, social and cultural facets, the mastery of the latter making it possible to construct an immaterial relationship which embellishes reality: every reuse/resell cycle proportionally and negatively affects the physical and emotional resilience components of a branded product thus progressively lowering the satisfaction derived from sentiment “to have made a good deal”.

The unwanted consequences of aggressive/predatory pricing strategy of digital secondhand platforms

The changes in terms of consumption behavior as well as the modifications in the competitive structures of so-called traditional industries induced by the circular economy are still far from clearly identified. Then, it is logical to postulate that the emergence of the circular economy is likely to affect the interactions between existing competitors and new players and the natural selection processes at work. This dynamic is explored here.

The structure of hypercompetitive markets that has evolved towards an increased diversity of natural enemies/competitors is likely to hamper pest control [53], which is likely to favor the emergence of new players such as secondhand digital platforms, which, thanks to a reinterpretation of the principles of the circular economy (value capture/extraction vs. value creation), may threaten the balance of the ecosystem.

Population and control ecology scholarly fields of study help explain the potential evolutionary routes of business groups and shed light on the (unwanted) consequences of circularity as practiced by secondhand digital platforms such as Vinted. It is likely that this already occurs in the clothing industry. Here, (we assume that) the clothing industry is a business ecosystem composed of a diversity of species,

that is, assemblages of natural enemies/competitors and other organisms whose behavior can be considered parasitic in nature.

First, as is already the case in certain natural environments, the context, that is to say, on the one hand, stricter environmental requirements, the choice of more responsible modes of consumption, and, on the other hand, among traditional/original players, a loss of competitiveness and failure to take environmental requirements into account, will favor an increase in the diversity of emerging species/competitors, that is, the multiplication of both horizontally (secondhand platforms positioned closely to Vinted that are Depop and eBay) and vertically (niche and premium digital resellers such as StockX and Vestiaire Collective) of predatory species.

Then, secondhand circular platforms (whose business model is grounded in value capture/extraction vs. value creation) have developed behaviors that can be qualified as a parasitic action understood here as a lasting biological relationship between two heterospecific living beings, where one of the protagonists, Vinted, benefits from a host organism – incumbent firms – to survive [54]. Here, it is neither about parasitic technology nor counterfeiting (although the purpose is ultimately identical), but to parasitically capitalize on an incumbent firm's reputation and related branded products. Most importantly, this relationship may have a negative effect on the host. Indeed, as in the natural world, competition and parasitism co-evolve and produce an idiosyncratic form of resource attrition along a mechanism by which predatory pricing and asymmetrical information distribution are progressively implicated in converting parasitism into direct competition, whereas there is initially no competitive relationship. Contrary to product counterfeiting (although some counterfeits are unavoidably sold on Vinted), this parasitic process is unwanted but nevertheless weakens both the reputational resources it exploits and produces substantial risk of damage as a by-product (Busby, 2019). The expected outcome would be that reselling secondhand goods substitutes for new product sales and/or increasingly reduces incumbents' prospects of being able to recruit outside their core target. This is clearly expressed by Vinted in the definition of its 'global mission': "Join our community of more than 75 million members in our mission: to make second-hand the first choice in the world [55]."

In such an environment, the most established competitors could benefit from a form of functional complementarity between predatory species, while the youngest or most fragile companies, such as the British brand Superdry, would become easier prey. To sum up, it is the qualitative effect of a predatory pricing

strategy that may then have the most significant competitive consequences, as short-term per capita consumer spending may increase at the expense of incumbent firms and (consequently) diverging growth rates may induce long-term variations in the thickness of the ecosystem [56] and the probability of negative competitive coexistence [57].

DISCUSSIN AND CONCLUSIONS

Recently, a growing and well-reasoned number of criticisms have been leveled to the promises of the circular economy and circular business models (e.g., Corvellec, Stowell, & Johansson [58]). Using the case of the second-hand platform Vinted, this article adds to this stream of literature by showing that its business agenda is mainly dominated by economic goals and that its contribution to sustainability remains disputable.

The implications are multiple. Its approach to circularity considers the combination of external resources (reputational capital and individuals' willingness to adopt more sustainable consumption practices while saving money) as a potential source of value. Opportunistically, the digital platform has built an economic model that promotes and facilitates the rationalization of these perpetual resources to their most productive (re)use while (fictively) expanding their social productivity. In this model, transactions between users formalize the value transfer of others' resources, without creating new combinations.

Paradoxically, although advocated and viewed as a potential source of value creation compared to linear product design and material use [59], substituting the concept of consumer with that of user does not determine a new contract between the company and its community of users, but an economic pact based on compromise. Though the value proposition engages consumers in responsible behaviors by reusing products, it is still in the 'buy-and-consume' economy as products are sold or exchanged as many times as possible until the cycle stops when the price level does not meet a demand anymore.

Paradoxically, again, value is extracted and re-extracted only through reuse, which leaves aside recycling principles and the related rearrangement of all components. The circular e-retailing platform known as Vinted is not an industrial system that is intentionally regenerative but a platform that replaces the 'end-of-life' concept with reuse. Indirectly, it intends (vision) to limit energy use as expressed in firm's corporate communications [60], whilst reducing waste through the advanced

design of materials, products, and/or organization are left to the firms owning the brands it resells. As such, it does not strictly adhere to circularity in the sense of a strict differentiation between consumable and durable components of a product: while its value proposition calls to 'join a community' built around a renewed relationship with goods and materials that would minimize energy consumption, it does not lead to new combinations and any deployment of resources towards new until now unprospected routes to value realization devoted to economic development [61].

Finally, while its predatory pricing strategy and global behavior are also part of company's efforts "to weaken, eliminate, or block the entry of a rival" by "lowering the prices to an unreasonably low (usually below-cost) or unprofitable level" (Guilftinan and Gundlach, 1996, p. 87), it may also lead to a price war and its side effects. Here, the predatory behavior materializes in both gaining new customers through

1. An increase in the number of product categories available on the platform and
2. The sale/benefit opportunity, while hiding price constraints and inhibiting existing members from leaving the community because it might mean accepting losses.

Such conduct is totally "independent of the predator's [Vinted's] own ability to perform effectively in the market" (see [62, p. 111]). This situation may open the door for unsatisfied and/or opportunistic consumers to switch to new competitors, such as fast-fashion companies, that are Teemu or Shein, who benefit from a more favorable cost structure and a regular update in their offers.

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